

TWO-BELT ROUND PRESTRESSED HANGING SURFACES WITH CENTRAL INTRO

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Annotation: *The article presents the stages of development of two-strip prestressed suspensions with an open circular center, the results of theoretical and experimental research and analysis of suspensions.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada aylana shaklidagi markazi ochiq bo'lgan ikki tasmali oldindan zo'riqtirilgan osma yopmalar rivojlanish bosqichlari, osma yopmalar ustida olib borilgan nazariy va eksperimental tadqiqot tahlil natijalari keltirilgan.*

Аннотация: *В статье представлены этапы разработки двухполосных предварительно напряженных подвесок с открытым круговым центром, результаты теоретических и экспериментальных исследований и анализа подвесок.*

Key words: *two-belt pre stressed, hanging, one-way upload, longitudinal raspor, inner ring, upper belt.*

The state of development of two-strip prestressed suspensions with an open circular center is divided into three stages. The first stage includes the period from the beginning of the use of suspension covers to the end of the 19th century, during which suspension structures were used only in bridge construction. The second stage begins with the last 10 years of the XIX century and lasts for half a century, during which suspension systems were developed by the Russian engineer V.G. It was used by Shukhov for the first time to cover suspension systems. Looking at the structures built in Russia and other countries, it can be concluded that suspension systems were used relatively little in the second stage. The third stage is characterized by the fact that there is a great interest in suspension systems, that scientific research works on suspension systems are carried out on a large scale in different countries of the world, and suspension systems are widely used in various structures.

Summarizing the results of the analysis of the research on suspensions, it can be concluded that the most optimal of all types of suspension systems is the two-strip suspension system. In this system, there is a stabilizing belt, which, compared to other systems, is less deformed under one-way loads, and the tension under the influence of temporary loads increases only in the load-bearing belt; in the stabilizing belt, it is reduced, and the change in the total value of the horizontal stresses on the support is small compared to other suspension systems.

The works of R. N. Matselinsky, V. K. Kachurin, E. N. Kuznetsov, G. E. Raynus, N. S. Moskalev and others were analyzed. For all methods, their characteristics and properties are described. Examples are presented that evaluate the constructive solutions of suspension systems with different geometric surfaces and loads. The graphs of changes in tension and oscillations of the suspension systems determined by various methods made it possible to assess the accuracy level of the used methods.

In fact, although the author of each method reached the solution in different ways, the results were close to each other. This situation indicates the correctness and high level of accuracy of the existing methods. Each method has pros and cons. Among them V.K. Kachurin's method is more accurate and N.S. Moskalev's method is more convenient.

In the calculation of two-strip prestressed suspensions taking into account the deformation of the support contour, the methods of creating prestressed flat and spatial suspensions up to now were analyzed.

Based on the results of the theoretical and practical research, calculation methods of two-strip prestressed suspensions were developed, taking into account the deformation of the support ring.

An effective method for the calculation of two-strip prestressed spatial closures, such as a system of two-layer conical shells interconnected by means of an inner ring, was proposed.

A decrease in the initial height of two-span prestressed suspension systems leads to an increase in their deformability and a change in its stress intensity. Therefore, it is recommended that the starting height $f / \ell = 1/20 \dots 1/12$ for this system be in the range.

1 - picture. Calculation scheme of a two-layer conical shell.

Initial indicators of lifting and restoring tapes (f_1 and f_2) it is recommended to determine the ratio with the following formula.

$$f_1 = \lambda \frac{B_2}{B_1} f_2 = \frac{E_2 A_2}{E_1 A_1} f_2 \quad (1)$$

$\lambda = 1$, and $f_1 = f_2$, will ensure that the effect of the suspension systems on the support ring is the best.

As the initial state of the surfaces, we take the state of the beams after prestressing.

Increasing the value of the pre-tension reduces the sags and tension in the tension of long-span suspension systems, which should be approached with caution, since the change in the value of the pre-tension requires an increase in the cross-section of the vanes.

In two-belt prestressed systems, it is appropriate to take into account the change in longitudinal tension force with the proposed method when determining the forces that ensure the joint operation of the belts in case of uniformly distributed and especially unilaterally distributed vertical loads.

When large-span two-belt flat systems are loaded with vertical one-way temporary loads, the law of change of the force ensuring the joint operation of the belts corresponds to the law of change of temporary loading.

Despite the non-linear operation of suspension systems, the law of independence of the influence of forces characteristic of linearly operating structures, when applied in our research, a difference of 5–25% in terms of sag and 3–10% in terms of tension in the vant was observed.

When a spatial structure consisting of two-belt prestressed radially arranged suspension systems is loaded with distributed loads, some ring-fixed suspension systems behave like a plane system, regardless of the flexure of the circular support ring.

Some suspension systems do not perform with the same intensity as when a symmetrical load is applied to the structure when a load is applied to one half of a spatial structure with a single circular base contour. In such cases, fluctuations are five times greater than when loaded with a full load.

The formula for calculating the horizontal displacement when one-way loading is applied to two-belt prestressed radial suspension systems (the difference is 19% when comparing the calculation results and experimental results) differs by 19% from the experimental results.

The performance of large-span double-span prestressed circular suspensions under various loads can be explained as follows.

Structural solutions of large-span two-span circular pre-stressed suspension covers of buildings and structures can be recognized as the most optimal solution in solving the

problem of using large-span covers for different regions from the point of view of performance against static loads and the ease of restoration technology.

In order to evaluate and predict the stress-deformation state of two-strip prestressed suspensions in the operational phase of the structural solution we recommend based on experimental studies, standard samples of vanes, farm models with vanes, vanes with different properties and different loading schemes (stretching, thermal treatment of vane samples), prestressing the valve, etc.) its strength properties were determined.

A test method was developed and a 1:100-scale large-span circular two-span prestressed suspension girder model was prepared and tested based on physical modeling.

Loading of the suspension model with different schemes and loads of different values, pre-stressing of the structures, performance characteristics during loading and unloading, as well as observation and analysis and evaluation of the performance characteristics of the structure in the loading process up to the limit stage of performance, that is, from the anchor of the outer support ring to the failure of the shaft, allowed to be observed and evaluated.

In symmetric loads, the tension in the upper and lower tapes of the vane was equally distributed, and the tension in the upper tapes of the vane was found to be 1.17 times greater than the tension in the lower tapes. In one-sided loading of the models, the tension in the maximally loaded part of the upper belt was 1.92 times more than the tension in the minimally loaded part of the opposite side.

The following conclusions are drawn for open-centered two-strip prestressed suspensions:

1. As a result of the conducted researches it is proved that the developed new constructive solutions of coatings with round two-girded pendant coverings with large openings are rational both from the point of view of static work and from the point of view of process ability of erection. Functionally, these designs solve the problem of overlapping unique buildings and structures of large spans of various purposes for different regions.

2. Based on the studies carried out, a technique developed for calculating two-ply prestressed pendant coverings with large inner rings, taking into account the deformation of the support contour. A system of equations for symmetric and one-sided loading obtained, which makes it possible to evaluate the strength and deformability of suspension systems taking into account the changing properties of the material and design features.

3. An effective method planned for calculating the spatial two-ply pre-stressed pendant coverings as combined with an internal large-dimensional ring of two-conical shells.

The results of the conducted research led to the development of engineering methods of calculation, improvement of regulatory documents, and were recommended for the widespread use of cost-effective large-span prestressed suspensions in unique buildings and structures with a circular plan.

List of references:

1. Research of trailing coverings of wide-span unique buildings by the modelling method US Axmadiyarov European Sciences review Scientific journal Vienna 5 (6), 275-276
2. Research of contour rings behaviour of suspended roofs NS Razzakov, US Axmadiyarov Conference proceedings I international Azerbaijan-Ukraine «BUILDING
3. Modeling of stage of construction and operation of unique large-span structures SR Razzakov, US Axmadiyarov, NS Razzakov Journal of Physics: Conference Series 1425 (1), 012100
4. CALCULATION OF PLANE DOUBLE-BELT RADIALLY LOCATED GUIDES FOR STRENGTH AND DEFORMABILITY, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT CHANGE IN MATERIAL PROPERTIES US Akhmadiyrov ME' MORCHILIK va QURILISH MUAMMOLARI, 70

5. The deflection of spatial coatings with periodic structure MN Kirsanov - Magazine of Civil Engineering, 2017 - cyberleninka.ru The scheme of the statically determinate spatial truss is proposed. Rectangular truss has a vertical supports on the sides and loaded uniformly at the nodes by the vertical forces. The ...
6. Экспериментальные исследования работы круглых двухпоясных предварительно-напряженных висячих покрытий СР Раззаков, УС Ахмадияров, НС Раззаков Будівельні конструкції, 580-587
7. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ РАБОТЫ КРУГЛЫХ ДВУХПОЯСНЫХ ПРЕДВАРИТЕЛЬНО НАПРЯЖЕННЫХ ВИСЯЧИХ ПОКРЫТИЙ МЕТОДАМИ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ СР Раззаков, УС Ахмадияров, НС Раззаков СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАСЧЕТА ЖЕЛЕЗОБЕТОННЫХ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ, ЗДАНИЙ И ...
8. Деформированное состояние предварительно напряженных двухпоясных вантовых покрытий при симметричных и односторонних загрузениях СР Раззаков, НС Раззаков, УС Ахмадиёров, ХК Хуррамов " Лолейтовские чтения-150".